

**AHMAD DONISHNING TARBIYAVIY G'OYALARI VA IJTIMOIIY
QARASHLARI**

EDUCATIONAL IDEAS AND SOCIAL VIEWS OF AHMAD DONISH

**ПРОСВЕТИТЕЛЬСКИЕ ИДЕИ И СОЦИАЛЬНЫЕ ВЗГЛЯДЫ АХМАДА
ДОНИША**

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Аннотация: В данной статье, автор анализирует вклад Ахмада Дониша в описании социально-политического строя в Бухарском эмирате в историческом произведении Ахмада Дониша «Истории Мангытской династии», круг проблем и актуальные вопросы. Две работы Ахмада Дониша посвящены в основном проблемам истории и государственного управления. Также исследованы основные факторы формирования просветительской и реалистической прозы, а также влияние политических и просветительских идей XIX и начала XX веков на формирование и развитие художественной прозы в восточной литературе

Abstract: In this article, the author analyzes the contribution of Ahmad Donish in describing the socio-political system in the Bukhara Emirate in the historical work of Ahmad Donish “History of the Mangyt Dynasty”, the range of problems and current issues. Two works by Ahmad Donish are devoted mainly to problems of history and public administration. The main factors in the formation of educational and realistic prose, as well as the influence of political and educational ideas of the 19th and early 20th centuries on the formation and development of artistic prose in Eastern literature are also explored.

Annotatsiya: Muallif mazkur maqolasida Ahmad Donishning “Mang‘itlar sulolasi tarixi” tarixiy asarida Buxoro amirligidagi ijtimoiy-siyosiy tuzumni tasvirlashda qo‘shgan hissasi, muammolar doirasi va dolzarb masalalarini tahlil qiladi. Ahmad Donishning ikkita asari asosan tarix va davlat boshqaruvi muammolariga bag‘ishlangan. Shuningdek, Sharq adabiyotida tarbiyaviy va realistik nasr shakllanishining asosiy omillari, 19—20-asr boshlaridagi siyosiy-ma’rifiy g‘oyalarning Sharq adabiyotida badiiy nasrning shakllanishi va rivojlanishiga ta’siri o‘rganiladi.

Ключевые слова: династия, социальное положение, политический строй, описание, анализ, мангыты, историческое произведение

Tayanch soʻzlar: sulola, ijtimoiy mavqe, siyosiy tuzum, tavsif, tahlil, mangʻitlar, tarixiy asar

Key words: dynasty, social status, political system, description, analysis, mangyts, historical work

"Taj-at tawarikh" by Muhammad Sharif bin Naql on the history of the rulers of Mang'it, "Futhot-i amir Shah Murad dar Iron" by Muhammad Sadiq Munshi Bukhari, who was a court poet and historian during the reign of Amir Haidar, "Zafarnomai" by an unknown author. Khusravi", unlike Mir Olim Bukhari's "Fathnomai Sultani", Ahmed Donish's "Brief History of Bukhara Mangits" is a sharp difference from the works written with the aim of receiving praise and emir's award, which are present in almost all the works of that time. did

Ahmad Donish is a scientist and thinker who created on the threshold of the 19th and 20th centuries. He actively contributed to the development of Eastern historical-philosophical thinking. He left behind a rich scientific and literary heritage - naturalistic, philosophical and historical works.

For Ahmad Donish, the founder of the enlightenment (modernism) movement in Turkestan, the conquest of Central Asia by the Russian Empire, the clash of civilizations is an impetus for the realization of the pains and problems of his country, and the emergence of the idea of self-realization. . He was one of the first to realize how much the emirate lags behind Russia and European countries. He considered the reason for the backwardness to be the obvious ignorance of the officials and state leaders, as well as the improper implementation of the education and training system. He angrily writes that intelligent thoughts do not reach the ears and that they are engaged in only four things: eating and drinking, littering, collecting and riding a horse ("from khordan, ridan, jamaa kardan and asp davandan" Among the above-mentioned works, Donish's "A Brief History of the Bukhara Emirs" is undoubtedly the most prominent and significant. (1885-1910) the beginning of the reign, that is, the events that happened before the author's eyes and he was a witness 'focused.

"Brief History of Bukhara Mangit Amirs" became known much later than the time it was written. Now it is difficult to say how familiar this work was to the author's contemporaries, because for a long time there was no mention of this work. It is not shown in any of the tazkiras. Even though S. Ayni was personally acquainted with Ahmed Donish and considered himself his student, he does not mention this

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work anywhere. Only in 1936, E. Ye. Bertels reported for the first time that he managed to find the manuscript of A. Donish's hitherto unknown work. Bertels called it "Treatise" ("Trisol") and gave a brief summary of it in his work.

In 1946, S.U. Ulugzada briefly described the content of this work in his research. The scientific community is familiar with some works of Donish's work, and as a result of scientists' research, a number of manuscripts belonging to Donish's pen were found. In 1959, the first printed edition of Donish's work prepared by R. Hodizoda in new Tajik graphics appeared with a number of abbreviations.

It should be noted that the title "Risola or a brief history of the Bukhara mangit emirs" is conditional. In the tazkiras and poems of Donish's contemporaries or those who lived after him, only Donish's poetic works and his famous "Navodir ul-vakoe" are mentioned, but as noted above, no information is given about "Risola".

E. Ye. Bertels, who made a great contribution to the discovery of this work, calls it "Biography of the Holy Bukhara Emirs" and comments: "I think that this title was added later, after the treatise was written. The author himself simply called it "The Treatise".

"Risola" is a valuable and interesting historical work of the end of the 19th century, but it is unparalleled in its content. Traditionally, it can be divided into two parts that differ in size and importance. In the short first part, the author only tells about the events he heard or received from written sources. It contains brief information about the last years of the reign of Emir Daniyoy and the reign of three emirs - Shahmurad, Haydar and Nasrullah.

It should be noted that Ahmad Donish does not cite the sources from which he got his information. Only two historical works are mentioned in the entire "Treatise": "Tuzuki Timuri" a thirteenth century work of incarnation and "Rawzat al-Safa" works of the nineteenth century. According to the scientists studying the historical works of Akhmed Donish, the currently known historical works on the history of the Mangits were written by local authors in the early or middle of the 19th century.

Donish's "Risola" differs from the mentioned works of his contemporaries by the fact that the events in it are given much more widely. In particular, Mirza Azim Somi cares little about the problems of public administration. According to L.M. Yepifanova, the researcher of this historian's work, Mirzo Somiy "never came out with a demand to reform the state structure of the Bukhara Khanate and did not propose any innovations or reconstruction in social and political life."

This is how these two authors evaluate the early years of Amir Muzaffar's reign. Sami: "At the beginning of his reign, Amir Muzaffar made justice his banner and threw a veil of generosity over himself. He treated the Amirs, Sipohis and other

inhabitants of the state with various gifts and mercy, and all classes were grateful to him. He performed commendable actions and displayed good behavior."

However, Donish evaluates the current situation of the khanate as follows: "Amir Muzaffar, who strengthened his position on the throne, dealt cruelly with the supporters of the implementation of the will. According to the will, the grandson, who was supposed to be Nasrullah's heir, fled Bukhara and disappeared. Amir massacred all his sons and grandsons, not one of them could escape in any area. Soon after, he dismissed the ministers and other high-ranking officials appointed by his father, confiscated their property, and appointed his loyal men in their place. The army and the people were dissatisfied with these actions of Amir."

When talking about the Sami emir, following the example of court historians, choosing flattering expressions, he focuses on the details of military operations in the war with the Russians and the neighboring khanates, while Donish gives a broader picture of the situation in the emirate. gives information.

The name of Ahmad Donish remained unknown to the Russian and Western European travelers and researchers of that time who were in Central Asia at the end of the 19th century and the beginning of the 20th century. The first Russian and European historians of the Bukhara khanate - Vambery, Khanikov, and others - created at the same time as Akhmed Donish, but did not provide information about his works. Even major experts on Central Asia, such as V.V. Bartold and P.P. Ivanov, ignored the historical source "A Brief History of the Mangit Dynasty".

The author of the book "History of the Peoples of Uzbekistan", professor A.A. Semenov uses Risola as a historical source. S.U. Researchers such as Ulugzoda, A.M. Mirzoev, R.Kh. Khodizoda, Z.Sh. Radjabov, A. Bogoutdinov, B. Gofurov have given information about the great political significance of this work in their research and have given high marks to the treatise. A.M. Mirzoev comments on the brochure: "This work does not raise the issue of reforming state institutions, on the contrary, the problems and shortcomings of the emirate are objectively revealed." R.H. Hadizoda, in his preface to the Russian edition of the treatise, states that it is "dedicated to the analysis of the history of the rule of the Mangit dynasty." "aimed at criticizing the entire political system of the emirate."

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